

Synergistic extraction of Fe^{III} using di-(2-ethylhexyl)phosphoric acid and 18-crown-6 in *n*-butanol

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Abstract : The liquid-liquid extraction of Fe^{III} from aqueous chloride solution by a mixture of 2-ethylhexylphosphoric acid and 18-crown-6 into *n*-butanol is reported. Spiked iron was determined by measuring its γ -activity at energy. Synergism was observed in the extraction of labeled Fe^{III} into *n*-butanol. Stoichiometry of extracted species in both individual and mixed extraction was ascertained by slope ratio analysis. From the extraction data, overall equilibrium constants for binary and ternary extractions were calculated. Thermodynamic parameters controlling the nature of the extraction were also evaluated from the distribution ratio values obtained at different temperatures. Such results are important in order to explain the extraction mechanism.

Keywords : Synergistic extraction , D2EHPA, 18-crown-6, Fe⁵⁹ radionuclide, *n*-butanol.

Introduction

Synergistic extraction is a process in which there is a mutual co-operation between two extractants used in liquid-liquid transfer process of metal ions. One of the extractant neutralizes the charge of metal ion while other occupies open co-ordination sites in order to make the metal surface as much organophilic as possible. Under such a condition, extent of metal extraction becomes more than the sum of the contributions of the individual extractants. Among the different classes of combinations most widely studied being the mixture of acidic extractant with neutral donors. Chelating reagents of β -diketones type have been paid most attention, although use of carboxylic acid, oximes, long chain alkyl amines have also been reported in case of transfer of transition metal ions from aqueous to organic phase. The most versatile class of neutral donors are alkyl or aryl substituted phosphine oxides. Due to presence of electronic effect in their structure, these compounds offer electron pair in order to fill in the co-ordination shell of the metal ions and at the same time their large anionic tail serves to transfer such metal complexes into non-polar organic medium. Acid organophosphorus compounds are known to be excellent extractants and particularly used for the purification of ligand likely to contain heavy metals¹. Among these ma-

terials, di-(2-ethylhexyl)phosphoric acid (D2EHPA) is available commercially and has been widely used in the extraction Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Cr^{III}, Bi^{II} etc.²⁻⁷. Mixture of D2EHPA and TBP was used to extract Zn^{II}⁴.

The removal of iron by solvent extraction especially by organophosphorus acid extractants has been widely studied. The common feature of these extractants is appropriate selectivity for iron. Among the organophosphorus extractants, bis(2-ethylhexyl)phosphoric acid (D2EHPA) is extensively studied for extraction of iron(III)⁸⁻¹¹. The kinetic aspects of this process suggest slow exchange rates in the presence of sulfuric acid⁹⁻¹¹. A number of new dialkyl phosphonic and phosphinic acid extractants have been commercialized in the last two decades. Good, Brayan, Juge (Jr.)¹² studied some of these with amine extractants. Miralles *et al.* have given a computer analysis of the equilibrium data for extraction of iron(III) with bis(2,4,4-trimethylpentyl)phosphinic acid (Cyanex-272)¹³. Demopoulos and Gelvet studied extraction of iron(III) from base metal electrolyte solution by alkylated derivative of 8-hydroxyquinoline and D2EHPA¹⁴. Some complicated techniques such as reductive stripping and hydrolytic stripping were also studied¹⁵⁻¹⁷.

Crown ethers have been often used as synergistic ad-

ditives to chelating, acidic or neutral extractants for the extraction of various metal ions e.g. multicharged transition metal ions¹⁸ lanthanides and actinides^{19,20} as well as alkali and alkaline earth metal ions²⁰. In such studies the macrocyclic rigidity, number and type of donor atoms were tuned to provide higher degree of selectivity of metal ions. Such a reagent D2EHPA has been employed to extract Fe^{III} from aqueous chloride solution into *n*-butanol in presence of 18-crown-6. Metal ion was spiked with ⁵⁹Fe and determined radio metrically by its characteristics γ -ray. Extraction results were optimised by several parameters and temperature dependence nature of extraction were utilised to explain the pathways in ternary extraction system.

Results and discussion

Effect of equilibration time : Preliminary studies on the extraction of Fe^{III} by D2EHPA in *n*-butanol show that the two phase reaction is fairly rapid and the equilibrium is reached within 20 min. Further increase in the time of equilibration does not affect the extraction equilibrium (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Variation of percentage of Fe^{III} extraction with time of equilibrium.

Effect of organic diluents : The effect of organic diluents on the extraction was studied with 0.05 mol dm⁻³ D2EHPA into different solvents and it was found that maximum extraction was obtained in case of *n*-butanol and minimum for benzene. The trend of extraction for organic diluents used follows the order : *n*-butanol (38.32%) > iso-amyl alcohol (34.87%) > chloroform (33.51%) > benzene (28.63%) > toluene (19.87%).

Effect of pH : The pH is a very important parameter for extraction studies. Much of the selectivity achieved in these extractions depends on adequate control of pH. Experiments were carried out with different pH of aqueous phase, at ligand concentration 0.03 mol dm⁻³. At first, it was observed that the percentage of extraction increased with increasing pH, but above pH 3.0 the extent of extraction decreases perhaps due to hydrolysis of iron. Extraction was maximum in the range 2.0–3.0, may be due to cation exchange reaction in which protons are released⁵ (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Variation of percentage of extraction with equilibrium pH.

Extraction of Fe^{III} with D2EHPA : The cation exchange is the principal mode of action of D2EHPA during extraction reaction. The oxygen atom of the phosphoryl group P=O ensures co-ordination with the ions extracted by forming products⁶. Again, it has been reported by various authors that D2EHPA undergoes dimerisation⁷ in polar solvents via the reaction,

HR = undissociated D2EHPA

Hence mechanism of extraction by D2EHPA may be,

Corresponding equilibrium constant at given ionic strength,

$$k = \frac{[\text{FeR}_n(\text{HR})_p]_{\text{org}} \times [\text{H}^+]^n}{[\text{Fe}]_{\text{aq}}^{3+} \times [\text{H}_2\text{R}_2]_{\text{org}}^{(n+p)/2}} \quad (2)$$

And distribution ratio,

$$D_0 = \frac{[\text{FeR}_n(\text{HR})_p]_{\text{org}}}{[\text{Fe}]_{\text{aq}}^{3+}}$$

Taking logarithm and putting the value of D_0 we have,

$$\log D_0 = \log k + np\text{H} + (n+p)/2 \log [\text{H}_2\text{R}_2]_{\text{org}} \quad (3)$$

Stoichiometric co-efficient for the extraction reaction can be determined from the plot of $\log D_0$ against pH and of $\log D_0$ against $\log [\text{H}_2\text{R}_2]_{\text{org}}$. From Figs. 3 and 4, the values of corresponding slopes are ~ 3 and ~ 2 respectively and accordingly individual extraction reaction of Fe^{III} by D2EHPA from aqueous chloride solution is described as,

Thus,

$$\log k = \log D_0 - 2 \log [\text{H}_2\text{R}_2]_{\text{org}} - 3\text{pH} \quad (5)$$

Fig. 3. Variation of distribution ratio with pH.

Fig. 4. Variation of distribution ratio with ligand concentration.

These values are similar to that of obtained by Beneitez and Ayllon²² for chromium(III) extraction.

Extraction of Fe^{III} with pure 18-crown-6 : Extraction of Fe^{III} from aqueous chloride medium by pure crown ether in *n*-butanol was also investigated, varying the donor concentration between the range 0.002 to 0.01 mol dm⁻³. The percentage of extraction was found to increase with increase in concentration but distribution ratios were very poor. The composition of extractable species was obtained from the plot of $\log D_s$ vs $\log [\text{donor}]$ and the data are fitted to a straight line equation that gives an average slope of ~ 1 (Fig. 5), indicating one molecule of 18-crown-6 is involved in the extraction process.

Synergistic extraction of iron(III) in presence of D2EHPA and 18-crown-6 : Preliminary experiments show that the extent of extraction is poor in case of pure donor

Fig. 5. Variation of Fe^{III} extraction with pure donor concentration.

and ligand, used in the present study. However, when ligand is mixed with donors a marked enhancement in the extent of Fe^{III} extraction takes place. As D_{mix} is always greater than D_0 , mixed extraction definitely leads to synergism. Synergistic coefficient (S.C)²³ defined by Taube and Siekierki as

$$\text{S.C} = \log \frac{D_{\text{mix}}}{D_0 + D_s}$$

where, D_{mix} = distribution coefficient in presence of bi-

nary extractants; D_0 = distribution coefficient in presence of only ligand; D_s = distribution coefficient in presence of only donor.

Apparent stability constants (β) of mixed-adduct in synergistic extraction is defined by

$$\beta = [D_{\text{mix}} - D_0]/D_0 [\text{donor}]$$

S.C and β values have also been shown in Table 1. The experiments were carried out varying the 18-crown-6 concentration (0.002 to 0.01 mol dm⁻³) while keeping

Conc. of D2EHPA (mol dm ⁻³)	Conc. of 18-crown-6 (mol dm ⁻³)	D_{mix}	S.C.	log β
0.22	0.002	0.407	0.411	3.397
	0.004	0.481	0.432	3.181
	0.006	0.527	0.425	3.051
	0.008	0.741	0.475	3.092
	0.01	1.062	0.510	3.165
0.31	0.002	0.616	0.431	3.239
	0.004	0.671	0.432	2.985
	0.006	0.915	0.502	2.973
	0.008	1.216	0.583	2.989
0.44	0.01	1.804	0.656	3.082
	0.002	1.083	0.356	2.952
	0.004	1.712	0.536	2.931
	0.006	1.827	0.531	2.788
	0.008	2.315	0.611	2.781
	0.01	2.658	0.613	2.767

those of D2EHPA concentrations constant. In each set of extraction, it is observed that D_{mix} increases gradually with increase in D2EHPA concentration and S.C also increases in same direction. Apparent stability constant (β) for ternary complex remains more or less same throughout the concentration range, establishing the mechanism of ternary extraction.

The plot of $\log (D_{\text{mix}} - D_0 - D_s)$ against both $\log [\text{ligand}]$ and $\log [\text{donor}]$ shows straight lines of slope values ~ 2 (Fig. 5) and ~ 1 (Fig. 6) respectively. Thus two ligand molecules and one donor molecule are present in ternary extracted species. Role of crown ether in such mixed extraction is that of basic donor, replacing water molecules from inner sphere of metal complex, increas-

Fig. 6. Slope ratio analysis in mixed extraction : Variation of ligand concentration at fixed donor concentration (B) 0.002 mol dm⁻³, (C) 0.004 mol dm⁻³, (D) 0.006 mol dm⁻³.

Fig. 7. Slope ratio analysis in mixed extraction : Variation of donor concentration at fixed ligand concentration (B) 0.0213 mol dm⁻³, (C) 0.0305 mol dm⁻³, (D) 0.0439 mol dm⁻³.

ing its organophilicity and thereby enhancing the overall extraction of metal ion. Thus, mixed extraction could be shown as,

Therefore,

$$K = \frac{[\text{FeR}_3(\text{HR})(\text{C.E})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]_{\text{org}} \times [\text{H}^+]^3}{[\text{Fe}^{3+}]_{\text{aq}} \times [\text{H}_2\text{R}_2]_{\text{org}}^2 \times [\text{C.E}]_{\text{org}}} \quad (7)$$

Since,

$$D_{\text{mix}} - D_0 - D_s = \frac{[\text{FeR}_3(\text{HR})(\text{C.E})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]_{\text{org}}}{[\text{Fe}^{3+}]_{\text{aq}}} \quad (8)$$

Substituting values of D_0 , D_s in D_{mix} expression,

$$K = \frac{[D_{\text{mix}} - D_0 - D_s]_{\text{org}} \times [\text{H}^+]^3}{[\text{H}_2\text{R}_2]_{\text{org}}^2 \times [\text{C.E}]_{\text{org}}} \quad (9)$$

Taking log values of both sides we have,

$$\log K = \log [D_{\text{mix}} - D_0 - D_s]_{\text{org}} - 3\text{pH} - 2 \log [\text{H}_2\text{R}_2]_{\text{org}} - \log [\text{C.E}]_{\text{org}} \quad (10)$$

Now,

$$D_s = \frac{[\text{Fe}(\text{C.E})]_{\text{org}}^{3+}}{[\text{Fe}]_{\text{aq}}^{3+}}$$

Thus, $\log k_s = \log K - \log k$

IR data of complexes reveal that the band due to $\nu_{\text{O-H}}$ is disappeared indicating the possible loss of proton on complexation and subsequent formation of an M-O bond. A new band appear in the spectra at 615 cm^{-1} of extracted complexes which is characteristic Fe-O bond and $\nu_{\text{P=O}}$ band has been shifted to lower wavelength compared to free D2EHPA which characterize the P-O-Fe bond in mixed adduct complex.

Effect of temperature : Temperature effects on the extraction of iron(III) by individual ligand and mixture of ligand and donor have also been studied also. In the case of binary and ternary extraction system, the higher temperature leads to increase in the iron extraction at this aqueous acidity. The equilibrium extraction constant $\log k$ and $\log K$ for the studied complexes were calculated from the equilibrium metal concentration in the organic and aqueous phase using eqs. (5) and (10) respectively.

From the values of equilibrium extraction constant at the temperature range investigated, the Van't Hoff equation was used to calculate the enthalpy change.

$$\log K = -\Delta H/2.303 RT + \Delta S/2.303 R \quad (11)$$

The plot of $\log K$ against $1/T$ is a straight line (Fig. 8)

Fig. 8. Temperature variation of equilibrium constant of Fe^{III} extraction.

where the slope gives the enthalpy of reaction (ΔH^0) and the intercept corresponds to entropy (ΔS^0) value. The values of ΔG^0 , ΔH^0 , ΔS^0 are shown in Table 2.

Data shows that extraction is entropy favoured but enthalpy disfavoured. The values of ΔH^0 are positive indicating bond breaking takes place during extraction. Again, release of water molecules in mixed extraction has been reflected by positive values of entropy. During adduct formation it is highly probable that extensive disruption of hydration sphere leads to the release of such water molecules.

Experimental

Reagents and equipments : A stock solution of iron was prepared by dissolving $\sim 1.00 \text{ g}$ AR $\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in deionised water acidified with little HCl. In order to spike the solution, an appropriate volume of stock solution of Fe^{III} was mixed with few drops of tracer solution of FeCl_3 containing ^{59}Fe , supplied by BRIT, Mumbai, India. Solutions of AR D2EHPA and 18-crown-6 ether (both supplied by M/s Sigma Aldrich) in *n*-butanol were prepared by usual way.

A Sambros model 335 digital pH meter equipped with a single electrode was used for pH measurements. Radio-

Table 2. Thermodynamic parameters

System	ΔH (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS (J mol ⁻¹ T ⁻¹)	ΔG (kJ mol ⁻¹)
Metal ion + ligand	(+) 40.98	(+) 75.82	(+) 18.39
Metal ion + ligand + donor	(+) 47.10	(+) 148.19	(+) 2.50

activity of ^{59}Fe was measured by a γ -ray spectrometer containing NaI(Tl) detector and S.C analyser supplied by Nucleonix India. IR data were recorded in a Perkin-Elmer FT-IR model RX1 spectrometer.

General extraction procedure : In the general extraction procedure, an aqueous solution containing $\sim 100 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of Fe^{III} labelled with ^{59}Fe was adjusted to pH 3 and equilibrated for 20 min with an equal volume of organic phase containing D2EHPA in *n*-butanol and to keep the ionic strength fixed, aqueous solution was always added with 0.1 M NaClO_4 before extraction. For synergistic studies, the organic phase was a mixture of ligand and the donor in desired ratio. After equilibrium, the radio activities of both of the aqueous and organic phases were measured by gamma ray spectrometer and from the data obtained, distribution ratio was calculated. For the study of the temperature effect, equilibrations were carried out in a temperature controlled mechanical shaker, after which distribution ratio were determined in usual way.

$$D = \frac{\text{Radioactivity in organic phase per mL}}{\text{Radioactivity in aqueous phase per mL}}$$

Conclusions

Extractions of Fe^{III} with D2EHPA in aliphatic organic solvent occur via cation exchange mechanism. However, in mixed extraction water molecules associated in inner sphere of metal ion are replaced by donor like 18-crown-6. Postulation of such reaction pathways are supported by the endothermic nature of ternary extraction with subsequent positive values of entropy changes. This is clearly indicative of formation of inner sphere complex by the present combination of ligand and donor. The ligand perhaps behaves as monodentate one in both binary and ternary extractions.

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